

Occurrence of smaller rice leafminer *Hydrellia griseola* (Fallen) (Diptera:Ephydriidae) in the Philippines

A. T. Barrion, research assistant, and J. A. Litsinger, entomologist, Entomology Department, International Rice Research Institute

Until now, two species of ephydrid flies have been known to attack rice plants in the Philippines: whorl maggot *Hydrellia philippina*) and root maggot *Notiphila spinosa* Cresson. *Hydrellia sasakii* Yuasa and Isitani was formerly confused with *H. philippina* and no longer is valid in the Philippines.

In 1979-80, a third ephydrid rice pest *H. griseola* (Fallen), known as the smaller rice leaf-miner, was collected by D-VAC suction machine from rice at the IRRI experimental farm (identified by Dr. Philip J. Clausen, University of Minnesota, USA). *H. griseola* was widely distributed mainly in temperate regions of Asia (Japan and Korea), Europe (France, Italy, and Germany), and North and South America. In the Asian tropics it has been found only in Malaysia and the Philippines. The adult *H. griseola* can be distinguished from *H. philippina* by a number of morphological characters (see table).

Characters that distinguish <i>H. griseola</i> from <i>H. philippina</i> . ^{a/}			
Character	<i>H. griseola</i>	<i>H. philippina</i>	
Body	Length (mm) female	2.04-2.08	2.22-2.25
	male	1.62-1.64	2.10-2.14
Head	Facial carina	grayish-white	silvery
	Width (mm)	0.63-0.66	0.75-0.83
	Height (mm)	0.46-0.58	0.64-0.66
	Width vs height	Broader than long	Both longer and broader compared to <i>H. griseola</i>
Compound eye	Color	Brown	Reddish brown
	Height (mm)	0.44-0.48	0.58-0.59
	Width (mm)	0.24-0.36	0.40-0.43
Distance from ptilinal suture to anterior ocellus (mm)		0.044-0.50	0.056-0.060
Distance between 2 posterior ocelli (mm)		0.10-0.12	0.14-0.15
Distance from anterior to posterior ocellus (mm)		0.08-0.10	0.12-0.15
Antenna			
Size and shape of 3rd segment from base (mm)		As long as broad (0.080-0.085)	
Number of hairs arising from arista		7-8	8-9
Distance between antennal bases (mm)		0.160-0.164	0.18-0.185
Thorax		Dorsally blue green with light brown tinge and grayish-white margins	Grayish brown
Wing	Length (mm)	1.70-2.20	2.42-2.48
	Width (mm)	0.60-0.76	0.80-0.84
	Cross veins	Cross vein 2 exactly 3x longer than 1	Cross vein 1 shorter than 1/3 the length of cross vein 2
	Haltere	Lemon yellow	Pale yellow
Legs		Femora and tibiae metallic blue-green to dark gray except the yellow brown first (inner) tarsal segment and reddish brown to black remaining segments	Golden to yellowish brown except grayish white femora and reddish brown last tarsal segment
	Coxa 1	Grayish white	Yellow with silvery base
	Apical inner half of femur 1	With a row of 12-13 minute spines	With a row of 10-14 prominent spines
Abdomen		Tergites with numerous setae, greenish-brown in color with grayish white margins	Tergites with fewer setae, grayish brown in color with silvery margins
	Length (mm)	1.09-1.40	2.08-2.10

^{a/} Measurements were based on 6 specimens of *Hydrellia griseola* and 48 of *H. philippina*